

PROPERTY CHARACTERIZATION OF METAL COMPLEX SULPHAPYRIDINE USED IN TREAT CANCER TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT:

When given as a metal complex, a lot of medications have altered pharmacological and toxicological potentials. Because each sulphonamide has one free amino group, they all have a flexible chemistry and provide intriguing potential ligands. One of the key individuals in the sulfa family is sulphapyridine (SPY). As an antimicrobial, anti-thyroid, and anti-diabetic medication, sulphapyridine is frequently used. Sulphapyridine is widely used as an antibacterial, antithyroid and antidiabetic drug. In this paper, modification of SPY was developed and characterized the various material properties. We create the metal (mercury) complex of SPY using a chemical root and reflux procedure in order to search for a modified and substitute for it. This complex is then examined using a few spectroscopic methods, including FT-IR, NMR, and PL. The relationship between infrared light and matter is the focus of IR spectroscopy. Energy absorbed by changes in the nuclear spin state is discovered using NMR spectroscopy. Any kind of substance may emit light after absorbing photons, which is known as PL spectroscopy. Powder XRD data of the metal (mercury) complex of SPY is recorded using Rigaku Ultima IV X-ray diffractometer. All this work includes a part of the development of a drug which is used to treat cancer.

Keywords: Fourier transform Infrared (FT-IR), Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), PL (Photoluminescence), XRD (X-ray diffraction), metal(mercury) complex, Sulphapyridine (SPY).

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INTRODUCTION

Sulphapyridine (SPY or SPrd) (Formula: $C_{11}H_{11}N_3O_2S$) is one of the important sulpha family members. In addition to being a by-product of the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicine sulfasalazine, sulphapyridine is a short-acting sulphonamide antibiotic. Most sulphonamides are readily absorbed orally. Although they do not really kill the germs, sulphonamides may stop bacterial growth [1]. One of the most interesting and educational chapters in medicinal chemistry is on the creation of sulphonamides, which emphasizes the need for careful planning and chance in the development of new drugs. The current age of chemotherapy began with the early 1930s discovery of sulphonamides' antibacterial properties. The potential power of molecular modification in drug development was later realized as a link between the chemical structure of this substance and its pharmacological reaction [2]. The sulphonamides are widely distributed throughout all tissues. The bacterial enzyme dihydropteroate synthesis is competitively inhibited by sulphapyridine. When these organisms metabolize the substrate para-aminobenzoic acid (PABA), the blocked reaction is required for the development of folic acid. In the realm of bioinorganic chemistry, metal complexes of sulphonamides have been extensively researched and are of significant interest [3,4]. As an example, the Ag (I)-sulfadiazine complex is used to treat burns in people [5,6], while the Zn (II)-sulfadiazine complex is used to keep animals with burns from contracting germs [6,7]. Because of its size and structure, mercury has a different co-ordination chemistry than the majority of other

transition metals. The prevalence of drug-resistant isolated bacterial strains in the population has grown to an alarming level, which is a significant related concern. Due to these factors, the need for new and improved chemotherapy drugs has grown, and the quest for novel molecules with antimicrobial action is now a key area of study [8-10]. Due to their pharmacological features, such as antibacterial activity, sulphonamides, and their many derivatives are particularly widely employed in medicine. They prevent bacterial metabolism from using p-aminobenzoic acid (PABA), an important growth factor, in the synthesis of tetrahydrofolic acid [11]. With this context, the current study discusses the synthesis, characterisation (IR, NMR, PL, and XRD) of mercury complex with sulphapyridine, and antibacterial activity to help in understanding the regulation of the antibacterial behavior of ligands upon complexation. The reaction of mercury (Hg) with sulphapyridine is shown in Figure 1. [12].

Figure 1: Reaction of Mercury (Hg) With Sulphapyridine and Bonding Structure of Hg- Sulphapyridine [12]

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Mercury (II) acetate metal

Mercury (II) acetate is easily accessible. The acetate anion, a polyatomic univalent ion made up of two carbon atoms ionically linked to three hydrogen and two oxygen atoms (CH_3COO), is present in all metallic acetates, which are inorganic salts made up of a metal cation and the acetate anion. The synthesis of catalysts, ultra-pure chemicals, and nanoscale materials may all be started using acetates, which are a great precursor. We have procured Hg acetate from Alfa Aesar. The structure of Hg Acetate (Formula: $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{Hg}$) is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Bonding Structure of Hg Acetate

2.2 Synthesis of Metal Complex of Sulphapyridine by Reflux Method: -

Reflux is a term used to describe an experimental technique in which the solvent and solute are heated in a reaction mixture and a condenser is used to cause the solvent to condense back into the reaction flask. A quick and effective approach to keep the temperature of a reaction mixture constant is to reflux the mixture.

The hood was set up with a stirrer, hot plate, and ring support for the reflux equipment. The stirrer was mounted with a heated mantle. The neck of the round-bottomed distillation flask was fastened to the ring stand, and it was retained within the heating mantle. The flask is placed directly over the center of the stirrer plate. Then, we used a funnel to measure out the reactants and solvent to be used in the reaction and put them to the reaction flask. To complete the arrangement, a magnetic stir bar was placed inside the flask. Figure 3 depicts the reflux device.

Figure 3: Reflux Apparatus

To stabilize the apparatus, we placed a condenser tube inside the flask and secured it with a clamp at the top junction. After that, by attaching the water hoses to the condenser so that water is "in" at the bottom and drains "out" to the sink at the top. The reaction flask's contents will start to bubble as the equipment becomes hotter. When the solvent vaporizes and ascends into the condenser tube, where it is cooler, the refluxing process will really start. The solvent will return to the liquid phase and drop into the reaction flask when the vapour passes through the condenser.

Procedure

- Firstly, all the lab equipment like beakers, capillary, specula and test tubes are cleaned with tap water. All this equipment is cleaned with the help of lab-wash. Then, the equipment is cleaned thoroughly with acetone to evaporate all water molecules within it.
- The cleaned equipment is kept in the oven up to a temperature of around 180 °C for 30 to 40 minutes to remove the moisture. To start with ligand: metal ratio 2:1, i.e., sulphapyridine is taken twice its molar weight into one of the beakers in which methanol (25 ml) is added to get it dissolved as shown in Figure 4 (a).
- The transition metal Hg (II) acetate is taken as decided for a 2:1 ratio into another beaker in which distilled water is added as shown in Figure 4 (b). It is a homogeneous mixture composed of only one phase. Here ligand is SPY and metal salt is Hg. Ligand: metal is taken in 2:1 proportion. SPY is dissolved into methanol and Hg (II) acetate is dissolved into distilled water. Both are added together into a round bottom flask and these solutions are added into a new beaker as shown in Figure 4 (c)

- Continuously providing a mechanical stirrer to this solution for 5 to 6 hours, results in white coloured precipitate as shown in Figure 4 (d). The precipitate is taken out by filtering the solution and allowing it to dry. Took precipitate into a clean container. Now, the compound is ready for characterization.

Figure 4: Experimental Process of Reflux Method

- Few spectroscopic characterization techniques are used to know whether the sample is prepared or not and spectroscopic analysis and the 3D structure of the sample by powder XRD is done.

2.3 Characterization Techniques

The SPY and Hg-SPY IR spectra were captured between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} . The mid-infrared, which ranges between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} (wavelength 2.5 to 25 μm), may be used to study the basic vibrations and associated rotational-vibrational structure. Using a Bruker Avance 111 spectrometer, the ^1H NMR spectra of SPY and Hg-SPY were recorded from the complex's solution in d^6 -DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide). Data from the SICART lab's PL system were captured. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) using a Rigaku Ultima IV powder X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu}(\text{K}\alpha)$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406$) was used to examine the structural phase studies of SPY and Hg-SPY.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 IR Spectroscopy

3.1.1 IR Spectra of Sulphapyridine and Hg-Sulphapyridine

IR Spectra of SPY and synthesized metallic complex of SPY are recorded at SICART. Recorded data are depicted in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 below [13].

Figure 5: IR spectra of Sulphapyridine (SPY or SPrd)

Figure 6: IR spectra of Hg-Sulphapyridine (SPrd + Hg)

3.1.2 Analysis of IR spectra

By carefully comparing their spectra with those of the free ligand, the IR spectra of the free ligand and the metal complexes are examined and assigned in order to shed light on the manner of bonding and the impact of the metal ion on the ligand. The free ligand's IR spectra are contrasted with those of the complex, which were collected in the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . A preliminary assignment of the most significant bands is provided in Table 1 based on a few generic sources and earlier research on complexes with sulphonamide.

Table 1: Characteristics IR Bands (Cm^{-1}) of the Spectra of Sulphapyridine and the Newly Synthesized Compound

Assignment	SPY	Hg-SPY
N-H	3106.55	-
$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NH}_2)$	3416.46	3454.07
$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NH}_2)$	3310.02	3379.39
$\Delta(\text{NH}_2)$	1637.81	1624.01
U-phenyl ring	1585.99, 1523.26	1592.96, 1545.47
$(\text{SO}_2)_{\text{as}}$	1323.28, 1302.72	1330.92, 1350.13
$(\text{SO}_2)_{\text{sy}}$	1181.97	1180.55
U(S-N)	998.61, 947.03	1020.81, 969.97

Indicating the effects of the modification in their hydrogen bonding strategy, the symmetric and antisymmetric bands allocated to (NH_2) in the ligand (3416.46 and 3310.02 cm^{-1}) are transferred to larger wave numbers in the complex (3454.07 and 3379.39 cm^{-1}). This shifting to higher frequencies is consistent with the shortening of the (S-N) bond length, which has been seen in the complex crystal, and is due to the coordinated metal's influence on the (S-N) shifted by roughly $15\text{-}20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to higher wave numbers in complex.

It is confirmed that the $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ moiety has been deprotonated by the absence of the peak for the sulphonamidic (S-N) group in the free ligand at around 3106.55 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the complex. The observed modifications imply that a mercury atom has been bound to the nitrogen of the sulphonamide.

3.2 NMR Spectroscopy

3.2.1 NMR Spectra of Sulphapyridine and Hg-Sulphapyridine

Each peak in the NMR spectrum represents a group of nuclei in the same magnetic environment and corresponds to a different applied field intensity. The method is helpful for identifying the structure of organic, inorganic, and polymer compounds. Figures 7 and 8 show the SPY and Hg-SPY NMR spectra, respectively [14-16].

Figure 7: NMR spectra of Sulphapyridine

Figure 8: NMR spectra of Hg-Sulphapyridine

3.2.2 Analysis of NMR Spectra

Due to the complex's insoluble nature in less polar solvents, ¹H NMR spectra from the complex's solution in d⁶-DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) were obtained. Chemical changes are measured in parts per million (ppm) with respect to internal TMS (tetramethylsilane). Table 2 displays the NMR data.

Table 2: ¹H NMR shift assignments of sulphapyridine and the Hg-sulphapyridine complex in DMSO-d⁶

Assignment	¹ H(SPY)	¹ H(Hg-SPY)
N(1)-H	10.983	-
C(1)-H/C(3)-H	8.101	8.197
C(2)-H	7.072	7.081
C(7)-H/C(11)-H	7.627	7.657
C(8)-H/C(10)-H	6.566	6.573
NH ₂	5.968	5.934

According to the results, even if the ligand is present in the complex, it only exhibits extremely minor changes when compared to the free ligand. The wide singlet at 10.8 ppm in the ligand's proton magnetic resonance spectra, which may be attributed to the sulphonamide NH proton, is the most remarkable characteristic. The fact that there isn't a proton signal in the spectrum of the mercury complex suggests that the complex is formed when the sulphonamide NH group is deprotonated.

3.3 PL Spectroscopic Characterization

A solid-state measurement of the photoluminescence spectra of a free ligand and metal complex taken at room temperature is shown. The ligand (SPY) and metal complex (Hg) have been shown to exhibit strong emission spectra of luminescence at 460.00 nm and 430.00 nm, respectively. Charge transfer from the ligand to the metal may be the cause of a metal complex's strong emission. Compared to the free ligand, this metal complex may find more applicability in materials that emit blue or green light [17]. Table 3 presents the outcomes.

Table 3: PL Spectroscopic Observation of Sulphapyridine and Hg-Sulphapyridine

Sulphapyridine		Hg-Sulphapyridine	
Wavelength	Intensity	Wavelength	Intensity
(nm)	(luminous)	(nm)	(luminous)
380	9.9986	380	18.21
385	12.278	385	22.002
390	17.002	390	24.728
395	26.589	395	26.32
400	45.452	400	26.682
405	78.429	405	26.873
410	124.05	410	26.683
415	172.46	415	27.682
420	208.63	420	30.467
425	226.32	425	30.993
430	231.22	430	29.31
435	230.18	435	29.522
440	226.06	440	30.5

445	219.22	445	31.256
450	211.76	450	31.315

Cont: Table 3

455	206.14	455	32.948
460	200.85	460	36.136
465	190.16	465	34.142
470	180.43	470	33.266
475	171.43	475	33.891
480	166.51	480	38.418

Both data show a change in the peak position. According to it, we can find emission wavelength by plotting a graph of intensity versus wavelength as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Intensity vs Wavelength

3.4. X-Ray Diffraction (Xrd) Technique for Polycrystalline Material

A quick analytical method is X-ray powder diffraction, mostly utilized for crystalline material phase detection and may provide information on unit cell dimension. The photographic technique of recording diffraction patterns is now supplemented in almost every X-ray diffractometer [18].

3.4.1 Measurement of Diffraction Patterns By X-Ray Diffraction

Graph of intensity versus 2θ is plotted for sulphapyridine and newly synthesized compound [19-20], shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12 below.

Figure 11: Graph of Intensity (Counts) Vs 2 θ (Degree) for Sulphapyridine

Figure 12: Graph of Intensity (counts) vs 2 θ (degree) for Hg-sulphapyridine

Over the whole 2θ range, the diffraction pattern has several peaks with varied and partly overlapping intensities.

The many techniques of qualitative and quantitative phase analysis may be used to identify the current phases and quantify their relative quantities [20]. With the help of EXPO 2009 software, the peaks are read and identified. An output file is generated by this software as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Software results for Sulphapyridine and Hg-Sulphapyridine

Sulphapyridine		Hg-Sulphapyridine	
2 θ (deg)	d-spacing (nm)	2 θ (deg)	d-spacing (nm)
9.099	9.719	22.159	3.83
10.638	8.316	23.227	3.739
12.46	7.104	23.798	3.648
13.999	6.326	24.4	3.584

Cont: Table 4

15.459	5.732	24.84	3.551
16.099	5.504	25.08	3.334
16.7	5.309	26.738	3.16
17.319	5.12	28.236	2.948
18.28	4.853	30.319	2.866
18.519	4.791	31.201	2.735
19.059	4.656	32.738	2.559
19.299	4.599	35.06	2.394
21.159	4.199	37.56	2.327

Here d spacing is the distance between two lattices. From Table 4, it is shown that when 2θ increases ranging from 9.099 to 21.159 then the d spacing decreases ranging from 9.719 to 4.199 with a high rate for sulphapyridine and when 2θ increases ranging from 22.159 to 37.560 then the d spacing is decreases ranging from 3.830 to 2.327 with slow rate for Hg-sulphapyridine. Here free ligand SPY is attached with metal complex (mercury). The data of the new compound from EXPO 2009 software are given in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Parameter of Hg-Sulphapyridine

Crystal system:	Monoclinic
Lattice parameter:	A = 9.46788 Å ⁰
	B = 19.44701 Å ⁰
	C = 8.59885 Å ⁰
	Alpha (α) = 90.00000 degree
	Beta (β) = 104.30597 degree
	Gamma (γ) = 90.00000 degree
Total number of observed lines:	25
Number of calculated lines: (up to 20 th observed d)	53
Space group: (centrosymmetric)	P ₂₁ /n

4. CONCLUSIONS

We characterized our sample by few significant spectroscopic techniques like FT-IR, NMR and PL, and the results from these techniques are summarised:

IR-Spectra

From the Infrared (IR) spectra, the N-H bond is absent in the complex of Hg-Sulphapyridine as well as a peak has been observed at 408 cm⁻¹ in the metal complex. This clearly indicates the binding of metal with sulphonamide nitrogen. **NMR-**

Spectra

From Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), our observations reveal that deprotonation occurs in the metal complex since N-H peak which is present in the free ligand is absent in the metal complex.

PL-spectra:

From PL, it is shown from the graph that the emission wavelength of SPY+Hg shift towards a lower wavelength compared to SPY. Emission wavelength in SPY is found at 460.00 nm and that in SPY+Hg is at 430.00 nm.

From powder XRD, it can be observed that the intensity and 2θ values vary in free ligand and metal complex. It reveals that the crystal system is monoclinic and centrosymmetric space group is P_{21}/n .

Hence, we successfully synthesized mercury complex of sulphapyridine and its single crystal.

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